

The Theory of Absolutivity

(Extended ChatGPT Version)

My theory challenges the notion of relativity by proposing that everything is absolute and nothing is relative. Here's a breakdown of the theory:

Introduction:

The theory presents a common scenario where two objects, an electron and the planet Saturn, are perceived to have different sizes. This perception is based on relative comparisons; the electron is considered smaller than Saturn.

Body:

The theory then introduces the concept of relativity, which suggests that the perceived size difference between the electron and Saturn is due to their distinct physical dimensions. However, my theory posits that, mathematically speaking, both objects are infinite.

Conclusion:

It emphasizes that while our minds perceive these objects as having different sizes, mathematics suggests that they are both infinite in size. This challenges the notion of relativity and underscores the theory's assertion that everything is absolute.

My theory offers a philosophical perspective on the nature of reality and perception, questioning the validity of relative comparisons in understanding the fundamental properties of objects.

Note:

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